

Derived from first principles fine-structure constant constants

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Abstract: If you don't feel the subtlety of it, you don't really like physics.

Key words: universal Gravitational constant formula, Coulomb's law, Basic atomic mass.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = 2\pi(m_e)[\alpha_0](c) , \\ \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} = (c) , \\ \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2 = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2}{2\pi(R_\infty)} , \end{array} \right.$$

Where (ϵ_0) is the Vacuum dielectric constant, (μ_0) is the Permeability of vacuum, (c) is the Speed of light, (e_0) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (R_∞) is the Rydberg constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_{atom}) is the Basic atomic mass, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, (G_N) is the Gravitational constant.

Reference: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Physical_constant.